

BRANDING, SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT, AND CUSTOMER PERFORMANCE OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

Abiodun B. Onamusi¹

Adeniyi I. Kadri¹

M. Trihudyatmanto²

¹Department of Management & Accounting Lead City University Ibadan, Nigeria

²Universitas Sains Al-Qur'an (UNSIQ) Jawa Tengah di Wonosobo, Indonesia

Abstract

The increasingly competitive landscape of Nigeria's financial sector has compelled Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) to strengthen their branding strategies to enhance customer acquisition, retention, and loyalty. Despite the acknowledged importance of branding in shaping customer perceptions, empirical evidence suggests that Nigerian DMBs have not effectively aligned their branding initiatives with measurable customer performance outcomes. Moreover, the rapid rise of fintech firms has disrupted traditional banking structures, underscoring the need for DMBs to leverage digital engagement particularly social media as a strategic branding and customer relationship management tool. This study investigates the effect of branding on customer loyalty among selected DMBs in Lagos State, Nigeria, and examines the moderating role of social media engagement in this relationship. Adopting a cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from 687 respondents using a structured questionnaire. The data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) via SmartPLS 4.0. The results reveal that branding has a positive and statistically significant effect on customer loyalty ($\beta = 0.462$, $t = 7.921$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that strong brand equity fosters customer retention and commitment. Additionally, social media engagement significantly moderates the relationship between branding and customer loyalty ($\beta = 0.287$, $t = 4.613$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that active digital interaction amplifies the positive influence of branding on customer attachment and satisfaction. Further assessment of the structural model confirms predictive relevance ($Q^2 > 0$) and robustness in explaining the interplay between branding, social media engagement, and customer performance. The study concludes that branding dimensions such as brand identity, image, positioning, and reputation are critical drivers of customer performance among DMBs in Lagos State. Furthermore, social media engagement serves as a vital moderating capability that enhances the effectiveness of branding strategies and strengthens customer loyalty. The study recommends that DMBs should strategically invest in social media engagement by maintaining active interactions with customers, promptly responding to inquiries, and sharing brand-aligned content. Highlighting customer testimonials, success stories, and loyalty initiatives across digital platforms can significantly reinforce brand credibility, deepen customer trust, and sustain long-term loyalty in Nigeria's competitive banking environment.

Keywords: Branding, Social Media Engagement, Customer Loyalty, Customer Performance, Deposit Money Banks, Lagos State, Nigeria

JEL classification: G21, M31, L84, O33

1. Introduction

The Nigerian financial system has witnessed unprecedented market turbulence, with Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) constantly competing for customer acquisition to sustain their market share and profitability (Asikhia et al., 2022; Onamusi & Adekunle, 2025). Although aggressive acquisition strategies have strengthened banks' outreach, their failure to deliver excellent customer experience continues to undermine brand trust and customer retention (Adekunle & Onamusi, 2025). A decade-long KPMG customer experience survey (2012–2024) revealed that Nigerian DMBs consistently fell short of the six core dimensions of excellent customer experience, indicating systemic weaknesses in customer-centric service delivery (Bhattacharya, 2022; Kadri & Onamusi, 2025).

The recent currency redesign and cash scarcity crisis, driven by the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) new naira policy, further exposed operational inefficiencies and the fragile trust relationship between banks and customers (Onamusi & Adekunle, 2025). While traditional banks struggled with service breakdowns, fintech companies such as Opay, Palmpay, and Moniepoint

emerged as more reliable alternatives. Preliminary evidence suggests that between February and July 2023, the number of retail outlets and customers adopting these neobanks tripled, underscoring a significant shift in consumer confidence and transactional preferences (Truong, 2024). This trend has triggered concern among conventional DMBs as they continue to lose market share and unrealized profits to agile fintech competitors.

In this increasingly dynamic and digitalized environment, branding has become a strategic imperative for DMBs seeking to preserve customer trust and long-term competitiveness. A strong brand signals reliability, consistency, and integrity; attributes that enhance customer confidence in a firm's products and services (Onamusi & Ayo, 2021). This trust, in turn, fosters higher satisfaction, loyalty, and repeat patronage (Sitorus & Yustisia, 2018). Effective branding also enables DMBs to differentiate themselves in a highly commoditized market by cultivating emotional connections and projecting a consistent image that adapts to evolving customer needs (Sitorus & Yustisia, 2018). From this perspective, branding functions not merely as

a marketing tool but as a strategic asset that supports customer-oriented innovation and sustainable competitive advantage (Kadri & Onamusi, 2025).

However, despite the consensus on the relevance of branding to firm performance, many Nigerian DMBs appear to lack a strategic understanding of how branding can be leveraged to influence specific customer performance outcomes such as satisfaction, preference, and loyalty. This conceptual deficiency often manifests in fragmented brand communication, inconsistent customer service, and limited emotional resonance with target audiences. A review of extant literature reveals that most empirical studies on branding have been conducted in sectors such as telecommunications, fast-moving consumer goods (FMCGs), hospitality, and entertainment (Adarkwah & Malonæs, 2020; Harris & De Chernatony, 2001; Islami et al., 2024; Onamusi & Ayo 2021). Few studies have systematically examined the nexus between branding and customer performance within Nigeria's banking sector, particularly among DMBs in Lagos State, Nigeria's financial epicenter (Kadri & Onamusi, 2025).

Moreover, the rise of social media engagement introduces new dynamics into the branding–customer relationship paradigm. Social media platforms now constitute critical spaces for brand communication, customer interaction, and reputation management (Onamusi, 2021). Through social engagement, banks can enhance brand visibility, promote transparency, and foster two-way communication that humanizes the brand (Khadijat, 2023; Quesenberry, 2020; Akin-Odukoya, 2024). Engaging customers through interactive content, storytelling, and personalized responses strengthens brand recall and nurtures relational trust. By sharing success stories, corporate social responsibility activities, and community impact initiatives, banks can build deeper emotional connections with stakeholders (Kouamé et al., 2022).

Despite these strategic opportunities, there is limited empirical evidence on how social media engagement moderates the interaction between branding and customer performance outcomes in the Nigerian banking context. Existing marketing literature has not sufficiently explained whether and how digital engagement amplifies or weakens the effectiveness of branding strategies in influencing customer loyalty and satisfaction. This gap is particularly relevant for DMBs in Lagos State, where digital financial interactions dominate customer experience ecosystems. Consequently, this study seeks to address the gaps by examining the influence of branding on customer performance and assessing the moderating role of social media engagement among DMBs in Lagos State, Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

Theoretical Underpinning

The Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT) emerged as an extension of the Resource-Based View (RBV) to address one of its key limitations the RBV's static orientation toward firm resources (Arndt, 2019; Onamusi, 2020). While RBV explains firm performance through the possession of valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources (Barney, 1991), it does

not sufficiently account for how firms sustain competitive advantage in volatile and technologically dynamic environments. To bridge this gap, Teece, Pisano, and Shuen (1997) conceptualized DCT as a framework that emphasizes a firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competencies in response to environmental changes (Asikhia., 2020; Onamusi et al., 2019; Vartiainen, 2023). Hence, DCT extends the RBV from a focus on what resources a firm possesses to how effectively it renews and deploys them to sustain advantage over time. This theoretical shift underscores that resources alone do not guarantee performance; rather, it is the firm's dynamic capabilities; its knowledge, skills, and adaptive processes that determine its capacity to remain competitive amid disruption (Teece, 2019).

According to Teece (2019), dynamic capabilities are underpinned by three interrelated components: adaptive capability, absorptive capability, and innovative capability. Adaptive capability reflects a firm's agility to reconfigure resources swiftly in response to market turbulence while maintaining operational efficiency (Romain, 2020; AlMulhim, 2023). Absorptive capability involves the identification, acquisition, and assimilation of external knowledge to strengthen internal competencies and innovation potential (Sjödin et al., 2019; Kale et al., 2019). Innovative capability represents a firm's capacity to continuously create new products, services, and processes that align with evolving market expectations (Kapoor & Teece, 2021; Daneels, 2002).

These dimensions collectively enable firms to sense, seize, and transform opportunities in dynamic environments, thereby maintaining long-term competitiveness (Jiang et al., 2020; Alateeg & Alhammadi, 2024). In highly turbulent sectors such as banking, where digital technologies and customer preferences evolve rapidly, these dynamic mechanisms are critical for sustaining market relevance and customer trust.

Despite its growing influence, DCT has been critiqued for conceptual ambiguity and limited empirical operationalization (Wilden et al., 2013). Some researchers argue that dynamic capabilities are difficult to measure and may not directly translate into competitive advantage without complementary resources and contextual alignment (Ferreira & Coelho, 2020). Others contend that their effects are often indirect, mediated by firm-level processes or environmental factors (van Lieshout et al., 2021). Nonetheless, recent meta-analyses and cross-disciplinary studies confirm the theory's robustness and versatility, highlighting its significant role in explaining firm adaptability, innovation, and performance in diverse contexts such as entrepreneurship, technology management, and marketing (Teece, 2019; Fabrizio et al., 2022; Habig et al., 2020).

This study is theoretically anchored on both the Resource-Based View (RBV) and the Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT) because they jointly explain how branding and social media engagement contribute to customer performance in Nigeria's Deposit Money Banks (DMBs). Within the RBV framework, a bank's brand equity represents a valuable, rare, and inimitable resource that enhances customer trust, satisfaction, and

loyalty (Sitorus & Yustisia, 2018). A strong brand, therefore, acts as a strategic asset that differentiates the bank in a competitive market and drives sustainable customer relationships (Nguyen et al., 2020; Onamusi & Ayo, 2021). However, in a digitalized financial environment characterized by rapid technological advancement and shifting consumer behavior, possessing a strong brand is insufficient without the capability to adapt and reconfigure it. This is where DCT becomes relevant: it explains how DMBs can leverage dynamic mechanisms such as social media engagement to renew customer relationships, enhance brand relevance, and sustain performance outcomes. Social media engagement represents an adaptive and absorptive capability; a means through which banks sense customer needs, absorb market feedback, and transform interactions into customer-centric innovations (Khadijat, 2023; Onamusi, 2021; Quesenberry, 2020; Akin-Odukoya, 2024).

Integrating DCT with RBV thus provides a more holistic lens for analyzing how DMBs achieve and sustain customer performance. While RBV emphasizes brand equity as a resource, DCT highlights social media engagement as a dynamic capability that ensures this resource remains valuable and relevant in an evolving market. This theoretical synergy reflects (1997) argument that sustainable performance arises from the interplay between a firm's resource base and its dynamic ability to adapt those resources to changing conditions. In the context of Lagos State DMBs, where competitive intensity and digital disruption are exceptionally high, the dual application of RBV and DCT explains both the possession and renewal of strategic assets. DMBs that effectively combine strong brand equity (a resource-based advantage) with high levels of social media engagement (a dynamic capability) are more likely to build customer loyalty, satisfaction, and long-term relational value. Hence, on the strength of this theoretical integration, the study hypothesize that: *H₁: the interaction between branding and customer performance of DMBs in Lagos State is significantly moderated by social media engagement.*

Branding, Social Media Engagement and Customer Performance

After reviewing strategic marketing management literature, evidence of empirical submission of how social media engagement moderate the relationship between branding and customer performance is largely unknown and this suggest this is first study to explore this interaction. In the event of this development, the researcher explored theoretical explanation and the conceptual relevance of social media engagement to position how the interaction can happen and path through which the interaction can be positioned. With respect to the theory, this study considered the contingency theory of fit as a moderator as noted by a scholar (Naidu et al., 2023). *According to the author, "When contingency theorists assert that there is a relationship between two variables ... which predicts a third variable... they are stating that an interaction exists between*

the first two variables", hence accentuating the attractiveness of the interaction perception in organisational studies.

According to the interaction perception, the effect that an independent variable (branding) has on a dependent variable (customer performance) is contingent on the level of a third variable (social media engagement), termed here as the moderator. In line with this position advanced by the contingency theory, which addresses fit as a moderator, this study posits that the fit between social media engagement as a contingent factor is a prerequisite for high customer performance. That is because social media engagement generates precise effect relationships that produce improved branding efficiency and overall performance (Aydin, 2020). The implication of the contingency theory is by leveraging social media platforms effectively, banks can build stronger brand awareness, foster positive customer interactions, and ultimately improve customer performance metrics, such as loyalty, satisfaction, and advocacy.

The conceptual relevance of social media engagement suggests that it provides an extensive reach, allowing banks to connect with existing and potential customers on a global scale. By creating and sharing engaging content that reflects the bank's values, services, and commitment to customers, the brand gains visibility and awareness among the target audience. Consistent branding across social media channels reinforces the bank's identity and message, making it more memorable to customers. Also, social media enables direct and real-time communication between banks and customers. Customers can ask questions, provide feedback, and share their experiences, while the bank can promptly respond, addressing concerns and resolving issues. This two-way communication fosters a sense of transparency, trust, and approachability, which are vital for building a positive brand image. Similarly, social media platforms collect valuable data on user demographics, interests, and behaviors. Banks can leverage this information to personalize their content and offers based on individual customer preferences and needs. Tailoring messages to specific customer segments enhance relevance and engagement, leading to better customer performance outcomes (Adeniran et al., 2024).

Also, by encouraging customers to share their positive experiences through user-generated content can be a powerful branding tool. Testimonials, reviews, and success stories from satisfied customers create social proof and advocate for the bank's services. This user-generated content influences potential customers and bolsters brand reputation, leading to improved customer performance. Social media allows banks to showcase their innovative products and services. By highlighting unique offerings, special promotions, and limited-time deals, banks can attract new customers and encourage existing ones to explore additional services. Effective promotion through social media can lead to increased customer adoption and retention. A scholar posits that social media engagement can acts as a moderator in the relationship between bank branding activities and customer performance. When banks invest in

branding activities and concurrently focus on engaging customers through social media, the positive impact on customer perception and loyalty is amplified. Social media engagement intensifies the effects of branding initiatives, leading to enhanced customer performance indicators, such as customer satisfaction, retention, and advocacy (Rachbini, 2023).

3. Methodology

Research Philosophy, Approach, & Design

This study adopts a positivist research philosophy to examine the effect of branding on the customer loyalty of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Lagos State, Nigeria. Positivism assumes that reality is objective and can be observed, measured, and analyzed through scientific inquiry. The justification for adopting this philosophy lies in its emphasis on empirical data, which supports the derivation of reliable, replicable, and objective conclusions about observable phenomena (Onamusi, & Olukolu, 2023). Accordingly, the study employs a quantitative research approach to measure and analyze the relationships among variables numerically. This approach is appropriate because it enables statistical examination of causal and correlational relationships while ensuring reliability and validity of findings through quantifiable evidence (Umukoro et al., 2023). A cross-sectional survey design is adopted to examine the relationship between branding and customer performance at a specific point in time. This design aligns with the positivist paradigm and the quantitative methodology, as it facilitates the collection of standardized data from a large sample efficiently and cost-effectively. Cross-sectional surveys have proven effective in investigating branding–performance relationships in marketing studies (Asikhia et al., 2020; Tijani et al., 2021).

Population and Sampling Technique

The study's target population comprises customers of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Lagos State, Nigeria. According to the Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS, 2022), there are approximately 56.5 million DMB customers with active Bank Verification Numbers (BVNs) nationwide. However, due to the unavailability of precise figures for Lagos State from regulatory institutions such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and NIBSS, the population for this study is considered unknown yet homogeneous, as DMB customers share similar transactional experiences and service expectations. The sample size was determined using Cochran's formula for an infinite

population, resulting in 600 respondents. To account for potential non-responses and incomplete questionnaires, an additional 20% (120 respondents) was added, yielding a final sample size of 720 participants. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants who met specific inclusion criteria: Must be an adult (18 years or older); Must possess at least one active bank account; and Must reside in Lagos State. This non-probability sampling method is suitable because it allows the selection of respondents based on characteristics relevant to the research objectives, thereby ensuring meaningful representation of the target population.

Instrument, Measurement, & Pilot Study Analysis

Data were collected using a structured, closed-ended questionnaire, chosen for its efficiency in gathering standardized data from a large number of respondents within a short time frame. The questionnaire was adapted from validated scales in prior studies (Hollebeek et al. 2022; Mogaji et al. 2021; Onamusi & Ayo, 2021). Responses were measured using a six-point Likert scale, ranging from 6 (Strongly Agree) to 1 (Strongly Disagree). This even-numbered scale avoids central tendency bias and enables more decisive responses. The instrument was divided into sections corresponding to the study variables: Branding dimensions (brand identity, image, positioning, and reputation), Customer performance dimensions (loyalty, preference, satisfaction, and repeat patronage), and Social media engagement (interactive, responsive, and content-related engagement indicators)

A pilot study was conducted among DMB customers in Ibadan, chosen due to their similar demographic and behavioral characteristics to Lagos customers. A total of 72 questionnaires (10% of the main sample) were distributed using convenience sampling; 61 valid responses (an 84.72% response rate) were analyzed after data cleaning. Face validity were established through expert reviews by academic faculty at Lead City University, Ibadan, feedback from banking industry practitioners, and input from the research supervisor. Necessary modifications were made based on these reviews. To statistically confirm construct validity, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed using SmartPLS 4.0, to compute the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Convergent validity was confirmed as all AVE values exceeded the recommended 0.50 threshold, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1:

Variable	Items Before Pilot	Items Retained	AVE	Remark
Brand Identity	10	8	0.787	Reliable
Brand Image	9	6	0.681	Reliable
Brand Positioning	9	6	0.644	Reliable
Brand Reputation	9	6	0.699	Reliable
Customer Loyalty	7	5	0.768	Reliable
Customer Preference	7	5	0.710	Reliable
Repeat Patronage	7	5	0.705	Reliable
Customer Satisfaction	7	5	0.649	Reliable
Social Media Engagement	10	8	0.697	Reliable

Source: Computed from Pilot Study (2025)

To test discriminant validity, the Heterotrait–Monotrait (HTMT) ratio was applied. All HTMT values were below the 0.90 threshold, confirming discriminant validity across constructs (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 2:

Construct	BIM	BID	BRP	BRR	CUL	CUP	CRP	CUS	SME
Brand identity									
Brand image	0.05								
Brand positioning	0.58	0.22							
Brand reputation	0.18	0.28	0.27						
Customer loyalty	0.12	0.30	0.18	0.11					
Customer preference	0.15	0.19	0.32	0.13	0.24				
Customer repeat patronage	0.51	0.15	0.32	0.04	0.02	0.18			
Customer satisfaction	0.05	0.03	0.08	0.12	0.16	0.06	0.16		
Social media engagement	0.14	0.34	0.28	0.10	0.01	0.04	0.15	0.285	

Source: Computed from Pilot study via SmartPLS version 4.0, 2025

These results collectively confirm construct validity, indicating that the measurement items effectively capture the intended theoretical constructs. Furthermore, reliability was established using Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach's Alpha (CA) coefficients, both exceeding the 0.70 benchmark (Hair et al., 2021).

Table 3:

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
Brand Identity	0.917	0.768
Brand Image	0.721	0.703
Brand Positioning	0.692	0.608
Brand Reputation	0.735	0.605
Customer Loyalty	0.728	0.698
Customer Preference	0.791	0.786
Repeat Patronage	0.742	0.703
Customer Satisfaction	0.741	0.763
Social Media Engagement	0.733	0.720

Source: Computed from Pilot Study (2025)

These results indicate that all constructs exhibit satisfactory internal consistency and measurement reliability.

Data Collection Procedure & Analysis Technique

Given that both branding and customer loyalty are customer-oriented phenomena, data were collected directly from bank customers rather than employees. The structured questionnaire was self-administered to the 720 selected respondents in Lagos State through physical distribution and electronic links to enhance response efficiency. Participation was voluntary, and re-

spondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality. Ethical standards were upheld following institutional research ethics guidelines. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to test the study hypotheses. Specifically, Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed using SmartPLS 4.0. The choice of PLS-SEM was based on its robustness in handling complex models involving latent constructs, its suitability for exploratory studies, and its ability to estimate both measurement and structural models simultaneously (Hair et al., 2021). This technique also allows for path analysis, mediation, and moderation testing critical for assessing the

moderating effect of social media engagement on the branding–customer performance relationship. Results were interpreted based on the significance level of $p \leq 0.05$, in line with conventional statistical standards. Compared to traditional regression analysis using SPSS, PLS-SEM provides more comprehensive insights into latent relationships, model fit, and construct reliability. Thus, it offers a rigorous and integrated analytical approach consistent with the study's positivist orientation.

4. Results and Discussion of Findings

Table 4:

Demographic Characteristic of Respondents			
Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	262	48.9%
	Female	351	51.1%
Age	21-30 years	287	41.8%
	31-40 years	175	25.5%
	41-50 years	148	21.5%
	51-60 years	70	10.2%
	61-65 years	7	1.0%
Educational qualifications	ND/NCE	112	16.3%
	B.Sc/BA/HND	252	36.7%
	PGD/MBA/MSc/MA	260	37.8%
	MPhil	14	2.0%
	PhD	42	6.1%
Years of experience	Others	7	1.0%
	0-5 years	133	19.4%
	6-10 years	217	31.6%
	11-15 years	98	14.3%
	16-20 years	119	17.3%
	21 years and above	120	17.5%

Source: Researcher's Field Survey Results, 2025

This section consists of background and respondent's information that describes basic characteristics such as gender of the respondent, age of the respondent and faculty. The Table 1 presents the demographic and personal profile of respondents used for this study. Demographic and personal profile of respondents as shown in Table 1: Profile of gender indicated that 336 respondents representing 48.9% were male while 351 respondents representing 51.1% were females, indicating that most of the respondents were female. Demographic and personal profile of respondents as shown in Table 1 by age revealed that 287 respondents representing 41.8% were between age 21-30 years, 175 respondents representing 25.5% were between 31-40 years, 148 respondents representing 21.5% were between 41-50 years, 70 respondents representing 10.2% were between 51-60 years, 7 respondents representing 1.0% were between 61-65 years, indicating that there were more respondents within the age 21-30 years. Furthermore, 112 respondents representing 16.3% indicated that they had ND/NCE, 252 respondents representing 36.7% had B.Sc/BA/HND, 260 respondents representing 37.8% had PGD/MBA/MSc/MA, 14 respondents representing 2.0% had MPhil, 42 respondents representing 6.1% had PhD and 7 respondents representing 1.0% had Others. Also, 133 respondents representing 19.4% indicated to have experience for 0-5 years, 217

respondents representing 31.6% have experience between 6-10 years, 98 respondents representing 14.3% have experience between 11-15 years, 119 respondents representing 17.3% have experience between 16-20 years and 120 respondents representing 17.5% have experience between 21 year and above.

H₀₁: Social media engagement has no significant moderating effect on the interaction between branding and customer performance of selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State, Nigeria

To test the null hypothesis seven, PLS-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) was adopted using the SmartPLS statistical platform version 4.0. The independent variable is branding, customer performance constitutes the dependent variable while social media engagement is the moderating variable. Data from six hundred and eighty-seven (687) respondents were collated for the analysis. The result of the PLS-SEM is presented in three model (see figure 1, 2, & 3) and a Table (see table 2). Figure one shows the path analysis, figure two shows the t values which confirm the significance of the path analysis and figure three shows Q² which confirms the predictive relevance of the structural model (t value above 1.96 and Q² above zero confirm a statistically significant effect and that the structural model specified is relevance). Each model comprised

of outer model which shows the factor loadings (correlation) of each item in relation to the latent variable and the inner model termed the structural model (predictive

model) which explains the interactions between branding and customer performance in this study. The table 2 provides a tabular representation of the information in figure 1, 2, and 3.

Figure 1: Measurement Model for Hypothesis One
 Source: Researcher's Computation via SmartPLS V4.0, 2025

Figure 2. Structural Model for Hypothesis One
 Source: Researcher's Computation via SmartPLS V4.0, 2025

Figure 3. Q2 Statistics for Hypothesis One
 Source: Researcher’s Computation via SmartPLS V4.0, 2025

Table 5:
 Summary of PLS-SEM Analysis for Moderating Effect of Social Media Engagement on the Interaction between Branding and Customer Performance of DMBs in Lagos State, Nigeria

Path Description	Original sample (o) Unstandardized Beta	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T	Sig.	Q ²
Branding → Customer performance	0.760	0.759	0.069	11.060	0.000	0.386
Social media engagement → Customer performance	0.280	0.216	0.049	2.538	0.011	
Interaction-term Moderating Effect → Customer performance	0.123	0.126	0.087	2.381	0.018	

Source: Researcher’s Result via SmartPLS Version 4.0, 2025

Figure 1, 2 and 3 presents the results of PLS-SEM analysis for the moderating effect of social media engagement on the interaction between branding and customer performance of selected DMBs in Lagos State, Nigeria. To establish the moderating effect in a PLS-SEM warrants the creation of a new variable termed branding*social media engagement. This interaction term’s influence is examined on the dependent variable (customer performance) and a significant moderating effect is established if the coefficient of interaction term has a p value less than 0.05. It is noteworthy that in a moderation PLS-SEM analysis, emphasis is on the moderating path result and with less attention to Adj R²

or the R² coefficient found in SPSS output for moderation analysis.

From the result in figure 1, 2, and 3, it is observed that the interaction term of branding*social media engagement has a path coefficient of determination value of 0.123. This suggest that the introduction of social media engagement has enhance the effect branding has on customer performance by 0.123 and this moderating effect is positive and statistically significant at p-value = 0.018. In addition, the SmartPLS provided the Simple Slope Analysis (SSA) which provide additional evidence to reinforce the presence or absence of a moderating effect.

Simple Slope Analysis

Simple Slope Analysis

Figure 4: Simple Slope Analysis for the moderating effect of social media engagement

Source: Researcher's Computation via SmartPLS V4.0, 2025

From Figure 4, the red line shows low social media engagement at one standard deviation below the mean, the blue line shows social media engagement at mean which indicates regular effect without the moderation effect and the green shows high social media engagement at one standard deviation above the mean and it reflects the moderation effect. Hence, the green line which is above the blue line suggest that DMBs involved in making high level of social media engagement enhance the branding-performance linkage. It is on the strength of the moderated analysis result ($\beta = 0.123$; $p < 0.018$, $Q^2 = 0.386$) and the Simple Slope Analysis obtained that this study conclude that social media engagement has a positive and significant moderating effect on the interaction between branding and DMBs performance in Lagos State, Nigeria. Hence, the study accept the alternative hypothesis one (H_{01}) which states that social media engagement has positive and significant moderating effect on the interaction between branding and customer performance of selected DMBs in Lagos State, Nigeria.

5. Discussion, Conclusion, Recommendations, & Future studies

The findings of this study contribute new empirical evidence to marketing and banking research by demonstrating that social media engagement significantly moderates the relationship between branding and customer performance. Existing literature provides limited empirical validation of this interaction, suggesting that this study is among the first to explore the moderating influence of social media engagement within the context of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Drawing on the Contingency Theory of Fit, this study supports the argument of Naidu et al. (2023) and Onamusi (2021), who posited that when two variables interact to predict a third, an underlying contingency relationship exists. Applying this theoretical logic, the

study confirms that the effect of branding (independent variable) on customer performance (dependent variable) depends on the level of social media engagement (moderator). In other words, the strength of the branding-performance relationship is contingent upon how effectively DMBs engage customers through social media platforms.

The results indicate that when banks actively leverage social media platforms to interact with customers, branding activities such as identity, image, positioning, and reputation produce stronger and more positive effects on customer outcomes, including satisfaction, loyalty, preference, and repeat patronage. Conversely, low levels of social media engagement weaken these relationships, resulting in diminished brand effectiveness and weaker customer connections. This finding aligns with Aydin (2020), who argued that the fit between organizational strategy and contextual factors enhances performance outcomes, especially when digital tools are used to strengthen brand and customer relationships. From a conceptual standpoint, social media engagement enhances branding efficiency through multiple pathways. First, it provides extensive reach, enabling banks to connect with customers on a global scale (Onamusi, 2021). Through creative and consistent content sharing, banks can reinforce their brand identity, communicate value propositions, and maintain visibility among diverse audiences. Second, social media facilitates two-way communication, allowing customers to express feedback, ask questions, and share experiences, while banks respond promptly to inquiries and concerns. This interaction promotes transparency, trust, and relational bonding, which are essential for brand credibility.

Furthermore, social media engagement enables personalization which means, banks can analyze customer data on demographics, interests, and behaviors to tailor content, offers, and experiences to specific mar-

ket segments (Rane et al., 2023). Personalized engagement enhances customer satisfaction and fosters emotional connections that drive loyalty and advocacy. Additionally, social media platforms encourage user-generated content such as testimonials, reviews, and endorsements, which act as digital word-of-mouth marketing and social proof, further amplifying brand reputation and performance outcomes. This study's results also align with Rachbini (2023), who found that social media engagement intensifies the effect of branding initiatives on customer performance. When banks combine strong branding efforts with active online engagement, customers perceive higher service reliability, emotional connection, and trust. This synergy produces greater satisfaction, retention, and advocacy which are key dimensions of customer performance.

From a theoretical perspective, the findings corroborate the Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT), which asserts that firms must continuously build and reconfigure internal and external competencies to respond effectively to environmental changes (Teece et al., 1997; Teece, 2019). In this study, social media engagement operates as a dynamic capability, enabling DMBs to adapt their branding strategies to evolving customer expectations and digital interaction trends. By leveraging digital platforms, DMBs can sense customer needs, seize engagement opportunities, and transform their service delivery to sustain a competitive advantage. Thus, the combined insights from contingency theory and DCT illustrate that customer performance improvements result not only from branding as a resource but also from social media engagement as a capability that dynamically aligns brand communication with environmental realities.

Based on the empirical findings, the study concludes that branding constructs including brand image, brand identity, brand positioning, and brand reputation have a positive and statistically significant effect on customer performance among Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State. Strong branding enhances customer satisfaction, trust, loyalty, and repeat patronage, all of which are essential to sustaining competitiveness in the Nigerian financial industry. The study establishes that social media engagement significantly moderates the relationship between branding and customer performance. The moderating effect reveals that higher levels of customer interaction on social media amplify the positive influence of branding on customer outcomes, confirming the theoretical logic of fit as posited by contingency theorists. Therefore, strategic alignment between a bank's branding initiatives and its digital engagement activities is a critical success factor in achieving superior customer performance. From a theoretical lens, this finding reinforces Dynamic Capability Theory, emphasizing that social media engagement functions as a dynamic organizational capability that enables banks to sense customer preferences, adapt communication strategies, and co-create value with customers in real time.

In light of the findings and theoretical implications, this study recommends that Deposit Money Banks should embed social media engagement into

their branding strategies as a dynamic capability. Active interaction, prompt responses, and real-time updates should form part of daily brand communication practices. Also, Banks should develop engaging and personalized social media content that reflects their brand values and directly addresses customer needs. Leveraging analytics from social platforms can help tailor communications that resonate with specific customer segments. Customer-facing employees and digital communication teams should be trained to manage social media interactions professionally and empathetically, ensuring consistent brand tone and customer satisfaction. Finally, Banks should adopt data-driven monitoring systems to evaluate the impact of social media engagement on customer metrics such as loyalty, satisfaction, and retention. Insights from these evaluations can guide continuous improvement and innovation in branding strategies.

Theoretically, this study contributes to marketing and strategic management literature by integrating Contingency Theory and Dynamic Capability Theory to explain how social media engagement moderates the branding–customer performance relationship. It provides empirical evidence of how digital engagement functions as a contextual fit and dynamic capability that strengthens brand outcomes. Practically, the study offers actionable insights for bank managers and marketing strategists. It emphasizes the need for digital alignment between brand identity and customer interaction to achieve sustained performance improvements.

Although this study makes substantial theoretical and empirical contributions to understanding how social media engagement moderates the relationship between branding and customer performance, it is not without limitations. Acknowledging these limitations provides perspective on the scope of the findings and offers valuable guidance for future research.

The first limitation relates to the geographical scope of the study. The research focused exclusively on Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Lagos State, Nigeria. While Lagos is the nation's commercial capital and a representative setting for digital banking and customer engagement, it may not fully capture the diversity of experiences and behaviors of bank customers in other regions of Nigeria. Customers in semi-urban or rural areas may differ in their levels of digital exposure, banking habits, and engagement with social media. Consequently, generalizing the findings beyond Lagos should be approached with caution. Future research could therefore expand the geographical coverage to include multiple regions across Nigeria or even conduct cross-national comparative studies within sub-Saharan Africa. Such comparative approaches would help determine whether contextual and cultural variations influence the moderating role of social media engagement in the branding–customer performance relationship.

Another limitation concerns the research design. The study employed a cross-sectional survey approach, which captures data at a single point in time. Although this design is cost-effective and efficient, it restricts the ability to make strong causal inferences. Branding strategies and customer performance outcomes are dynamic phenomena that evolve over time in response to

changes in technology, competition, and consumer behavior. A longitudinal design would help in understanding how variations in branding strategies and digital engagement affect customer loyalty and satisfaction over an extended period. Future studies may therefore adopt longitudinal or panel designs to provide stronger evidence of causality and track the temporal effects of branding and social media engagement.

The reliance on self-reported data represents another limitation. Because data were obtained through structured questionnaires, the findings are subject to common method bias and social desirability effects. Respondents may have provided answers they perceived as socially acceptable rather than those that accurately reflect their true experiences. Future studies could mitigate this limitation by adopting a mixed-method approach that combines quantitative surveys with qualitative techniques such as interviews, focus groups, or sentiment analysis of social media content. Such triangulation would provide a richer understanding of customer perceptions and offer deeper insights into how customers emotionally and cognitively interact with bank brands in the digital space. While the study concentrated on social media engagement as the moderating variable, other contextual factors may also influence the relationship between branding and customer performance. Variables such as perceived service quality, brand trust, and customer experience management could moderate or mediate the relationship in meaningful ways. Future research could incorporate these additional constructs to develop a more comprehensive model of customer performance determinants within the financial services industry.

The study's sampling approach also introduces a degree of limitation. Purposive sampling was used to ensure that only relevant participants active DMB customers resident in Lagos were included. While this method ensures the selection of knowledgeable respondents, it may reduce the generalizability of results. Future studies might consider employing probability-based sampling techniques to ensure more representative samples and enhance external validity. Despite these limitations, this study offers valuable theoretical and practical insights as it demonstrated how social media engagement acts as a dynamic capability that strengthens the link between branding and customer performance.

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